

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

D7.1. Plan for dissemination, communication, and exploitation

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	FULL NAME
ACF	Action Contre la Faim
CRS	Catholic Relief Services
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IAPHL	International Association of Public Health Logisticians
IHOs	International Humanitarian Organisations
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
REH	Humanitarian Environment Network
WM	Waste Management
WPs	Work Packages

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BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM

WORM aims to design guidelines and support actions for circular economy in the humanitarian sector. It integrates bio-based technological solutions, leverages procurement for waste reduction, improves waste management methods and prioritises the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component. Following a collaborative and multi-actor approach, WORM brings together medical and humanitarian organisations, procurement service providers, logistics providers, waste management services and academic partners.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392.

This deliverable is the first version of the Plan for Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (PDCE) as part of Work Package 7 on Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation. It provides the WORM partners with guidelines on the different communication, dissemination and outreach activities that are planned throughout the project, their schedule, and the partners' responsibilities. The PDCE will be updated at M12 (D7.3) and include any new and corrective actions that may be necessary to reach the pre-established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and ensure the appropriate impact of the action.

More specifically, the PDCE:

1. proposes a dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy and defines the objectives of the actions.
2. identifies the targeted audiences for each objective or main results.
3. lists the channels to be used.
4. presents a schedule of the actions.
5. describes the monitoring and implementation of impact assessment actions (through qualitative and quantitative KPIs).

The document is drafted by Euronovia (WP7/8 leader), with inputs from all partners. A final report on the project communication, dissemination, and dissemination activities (D8.2) is planned by M24.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

This is WORM's project Plan for Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation. It introduces WORM communication and dissemination strategy and activities.

INTRODUCTION

DEFINITIONS AND TERMINOLOGY

WORM distinguishes between **communication** and **dissemination**, in line with the EC definitions below.

Communication is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime. It is aimed at promoting WORM and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) WORM and (ii) results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Activities used for communication purposes are for example a public website, social media, or a newsletter.

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protection or exploitation of results), including scientific publication in any medium. It is the process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (e.g., research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, enabling them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project. Tools and activities used for dissemination purposes are for example a public website, press releases, publications, and attendance of events.

Exploitation of results requires several steps including identifying exploitation mechanisms and activities. It focuses on identified end-users to ensure impact and uptake of the results. WORM will integrate diverse activities along the project lifetime to enhance the dissemination and exploitation strategy, maximize the expected impact and boost the project sustainability for the continuation of the project after EU-funding.

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Communication and dissemination activities fall under WP7 and WP8 which are coordinated by Euronovia, with support from all partners who **strongly participate in communication and dissemination activities**, namely by:

- Communicating their activities and disseminating their results to their respective networks, for instance via their own social media accounts and websites.
- Contributing to the content of the WORM social media accounts, website, and bi-annual newsletter.
- Informing the other partners of relevant initiatives, activities, and events they could participate in.
- Keeping track of their communication and dissemination activities by filling in a dedicated reporting table available in the project's document repository (see Annex 1).

Disseminating results in open access publications, conferences, and other relevant events

1. GENERAL RULES AND PROCEDURES

1.1. COMMUNICATION WITHIN WORM

Communication among partners is crucial to exchange up-to-date knowledge and data on activities implemented within the different WPs and to enhance and optimize external communication and dissemination.

Internal communication is ensured through regular exchange of information via e-mail, through the WORM SharePoint and during regular meetings, when all partners gather to discuss achievements, upcoming activities, deadlines, and issues arising within the different work packages.

WORM uses a secure collaborative workspace on Sharepoint with an interface through MS Teams to facilitate the co-operation between parties and co-ordinate tasks ([WORM - EU Project | General | Microsoft Teams](#)). See deliverable D9.1 Project Management Handbook for more information.

1.2. USE OF GRAPHIC IDENTITY AND EU VISIBILITY

A common graphic identity has been defined to allow for better visibility and recognition, as well as branding of the WORM project. Therefore, all communication and dissemination tools and activities must refer to or include:

1. The WORM project logo (different versions are available depending on the background colour and document format)
2. The name of the project: WORM
3. Information on EU funding (as defined in Article 17 of the GA):
 1. Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must: (a) display the EU emblem and (b) include the following text: “Funded by the European Union”.
 2. Any communication and dissemination activity must also indicate the following disclaimer: “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”
 3. When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must be given appropriate prominence.
 4. Specific guidelines regarding the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027 can be found on the [EC website](#).

1.3. OPEN ACCESS TO SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Open access is defined by the EC as the online access to research outputs provided free of charge to the end-user (Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement). It is mandatory under Horizon Europe, and it operates on the principle of being ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’. The WORM partners are committed to publishing scientific publications in open access. WORM will follow the Open Science Policy of the Horizon Europe Programme and apply Open Science Practices to all methodologies, research results, deliverables, policy, and scientific publications, as well as to data that is not subject to GDPR. As required by the EC, all publications will be made immediately accessible.

The platform [Sherpa/Romeo](#) will be used to have a summary of permissions that are normally given as part of each publisher's copyright transfer agreement.

Further to this and whenever necessary, the addendum to the publication agreement provided by the EC will be used. This is an instrument that, if accepted by the editor, modifies the publisher's agreement, and allows the researcher to keep key rights to your articles. The coordinator will support the researchers for these administrative issues related to the communication with the publishers.

All publications and accompanying data will be stored in the WORM project community that has been created on **Zenodo** (https://zenodo.org/communities/worm_eu) by WP7/8. All uploads will thus be directly indexed in OpenAIRE.

2. WORM VISUAL IDENTITY

The **project branding**, created right at the start of the project, is helping all partners to communicate about the project in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner: it includes the project logo, project identity, and templates for Word and PowerPoint documents.

Figure 1: WORM logo

Euronovia proposed 3 options of logos during the Kick off meeting. The consortium has voted for this logo (see figure 1). The **WORM logotype** consists of a declination of greens to fit with the “greening the humanitarian sector” objective of the project. This logo is oriented towards the circular economy, as the circularity is represented with the O. We can also find a leaf in the O. A worm is crossing the letters but in a subtle manner. The typography is both rounded and serious. This logo has been chosen for its modernity, movement, and match with the missions of the project.

The **main font** is ITC Avant Garde which matches well with the logotype and gives a sense of fluidity, connecting with the idea of a worm. The secondary font is Arial.

This logo will be used in all communications (tools, deliverables, presentations, invitations etc.) to ensure a good recognition of the project. Specific guidelines on how to use the logo both on a white and dark background, as well as indications on its placement, font and colours are described in its **brand manual** (available to the EC upon request)

Figure 2: Extract from the WORM brand manual.

The different versions of the project logo as well as the brand manual are available for download on the project management platform.

Templates for the project deliverables, minutes of meetings, and PowerPoint presentations were created to be used by the partners for all presentations on WORM both in internal and external events.

Figure 3: WORM templates.

3. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

3.1. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the WORM communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities are to maximise the impact of the project by:

- Building widespread awareness about the project, its goals, and the importance of waste management challenges in humanitarian operations among the target audiences (see Section 3.2).
- Raising awareness about the potential of WORM and reach out to society and show its impact and benefits.
- Promoting behaviour change and encouraging the adoption of responsible practices waste reduction, reuse, and recycling among humanitarian organisations.
- Highlighting and showcasing the successful outcomes of WORM.
- Engaging with relevant stakeholders including local communities, NGOs, collaboratively address waste management challenges and fostering partnerships and synergies to enhance waste management practices.
- Running a local awareness campaign in the community to ensure the proper treatment of esp. medical waste.
- Showing how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible, notably in fostering citizen engagement through a project-based approach and contributing solving societal and environmental challenges.
- Disseminating best practices/guidance and making better use of WORM results, by ensuring they are taken up by decision-makers to influence policymaking and ensure a follow-up of the development of specific policies related to waste management in humanitarian operations.

3.2. TARGET GROUPS

The consortium has identified several target groups that have an interest in the WORM project and will use our results. These are being targeted by different communication, dissemination, and exploitation actions as well as networking and clustering activities, as detailed in the table below.

Targeted audiences will be refined throughout the lifetime of the project in relation to the various activities developed within the different work packages.

Target audiences differ from stakeholders’ categories which are groups of individuals who may be affected by or may influence the project.

These are the target groups that will best make use of the project’s results.

Table 1: Target groups table

Audience	Example of targeted audience	Objectives	Content & Channels
Humanitarian & medical organisations	Humanitarian and aid organisations, local organisations (e.g., WREC, REH, HULO, IAPHL), NGOs (LNGOs, NNGOs), medial sector practitioners, clinic, and field hospitals.	Share guidelines and recommendations, engage them in the project’s activities (surveys, workshops, etc.)	Website, social media, newsletters, press releases, co-design workshops, final conference & participation in academic conferences
Industry	Suppliers of humanitarian products, bio-based material suppliers (e.g. engaged through Innovasjon Norge’s	Uniformise the use of plastic type for the same product groups, increase the use of biodegradable plastics for single-use products, share	Website, social media, newsletters, press releases, co-design workshops, webinars, final conference,

	humanitarian supplier cluster).	guidelines and recommendations, engage them in the project's activities (surveys, workshops).	participation in academic conferences, targeted local awareness campaigns.
Waste Management organisations	Private and public sector, local WM businesses in humanitarian aid contexts.	Share guidelines and recommendations, engage them in the project's activities (surveys, workshops, etc.), engage with International Humanitarian Organisations (IHO), improve infrastructure/services.	Website, social media, newsletters, press releases, press media, non-scientific articles, co-design workshops, final conference, targeted local awareness campaigns.
Policy and decisionmakers at local, national, European, and international levels, donors	National and country authorities, local governments, DG ECHO for procurement strategy with sustainability criteria, institutional donors, Emergency Medical Team Coordination Cell (EMTCC), Global Health Cluster, Global Logistics Cluster and Global WASH Cluster.	Share guidelines and recommendations, demonstrate the benefits of WORM results to support EU policy, uptake of the project's results.	Website, social media, newsletters, press releases, press media, non-scientific articles, final conference, policy brief, targeted local awareness campaigns.
Scientific community	Humanitarian action, academics, public health, environmental science, development/policy studies, masters' theses & PhD studies.	Transfer of knowledge, reuse of the scientific data, receive support from the scientific community.	Website, social media, newsletters, press releases, scientific articles, final conference, joint actions with others EU/international projects.
European and international networks & projects	Bio-based Industries Consortium Projects (e.g. Bio4Human, Allthings.bioPRO, Deep Purple, Mandala BioBarr, BIONTOP, BIOPEN, BIOWAYS, USABLE PACKAGING, etc.).	Ensure the replicability of the project's results and support their sustainability, facilitate synergies between projects and initiatives related to circular economy.	Website, social media, press releases, final conference.
Citizens, media	Civil society, citizens from the informal waste sector (e.g., waste pickers), local communities, activist, individual donors, current and	Raise awareness about the project and its social and economic benefits, highlight the efforts done to green the humanitarian sector.	Website, social media, press releases, press media, non-scientific articles, workshops, final

	potential donors to humanitarian organisations.		conference, targeted local awareness campaigns.
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3.3. WORM messages

The WORM communication, dissemination and outreach activities are tailored to ensure that important messages reach our targeted audiences, and that the public at large connects with WORM.

For each different audience identified, a distinct strategy using targeted messages, means and language is being used. For each audience, we are trying to answer the following questions and adapt the message we are delivering:

- Why do they need to know?
- What makes the issue urgent?
- What are the consequences if no action is taken?
- What solutions are we offering?
- How does our work relate to their everyday life?
- Does it link to any broader societal issue?

These are some of the key messages that we are delivering through the communication and dissemination activities:

- Paradigm shift is needed in humanitarian logistics. In line with the Do No Harm policy, the humanitarian community should aim to **make the delivery of humanitarian aid more efficient, effective, while reducing the carbon footprint** and environmental damage of aid delivery.
- One **key challenge is the disposal of waste**, including packaging, toxic waste, and the use of materials such as plastics. WORM contributes in two distinct settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes.
- In line with the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, **WORM targets the entire life cycle of the materials and products used in humanitarian aid** and evaluate how they can be improved from a sustainability perspective, as well as introduce alternative bio-based materials to be used. This will promote the circular economy processes of the humanitarian supply chain.
- WORM focuses on **identifying bio-based solutions as alternatives, but also assesses the limitations** to their use from a wider systemic, humanitarian perspective. Particular attention is paid to bio-based alternatives to single-use items such as packaging materials, plastic film, and personal protective equipment as well as items that have previously been incinerated. The technical and economic viability of bio-based products will be evaluated through a technical assessment of their qualities in line with the requirements of the IHOs.
- In field hospital deployments, **medical waste presents an added complexity to waste management**, as the waste can include infectious, pathological, chemical, sharp, and radioactive waste. Unmanaged medical waste is a further health hazard and requires specific infrastructure to process adequately. All waste must be handled in a safe and hygienic manner. A significant proportion of waste is also toxic and different treatment options may also result in different levels of toxicity.
- Currently **waste-pickers form a significant part of the waste management infrastructure of many contexts**, and WORM focuses on increasing their dignity and health and safety through policies and programmes in collaboration with NGOs around the world. **WORM raises awareness for waste-pickers’ situation** in the short term, improves the processes of livelihoods from waste management **and removes the stigma** in the long term.

3.4. PHASES

The planning and execution of the project communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities require a schedule closely aligned with key project deliverables, milestones, and activities. In this framework, **our activities are organised around 3 phases:**

1. Phase 1 (M1-M6) on the prioritisation of product groups.
2. Phase 2 (M6-M12) related to the evaluation of bio-based alternatives and local waste management innovations.
3. Phase 3 (M12-M24) dedicated to policy recommendations and local implementation.

During the initial phase (M1-M6), the emphasis will be on developing a comprehensive communication strategy that outlines key messages, target audiences, and the selection of appropriate communication channels. In this phase, we are developing the project website and various communication and dissemination materials (MS, including the project graphical identity (i.e., project logo, branding guidelines, templates for project documents and presentations). In this phase, we are drafting the Plan for dissemination, communication, and exploitation (7.1). At the end of the initial phase, we will disseminate the results of the scoping exercise of commonly used product groups that could qualify for seeking bio-based alternative solutions.

Subsequently, **the 2nd phase (M6-M12)** will focus on specific communication and dissemination activities tailored to the unique characteristics of each Work Packages. In this phase, we are also drafting the batch #1 of practice abstracts (7.2) and the mid-report on dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities (7.3). Dissemination will focus on the sustainability assessment of bio-based solutions to be integrated into procurement processes, analysis of local innovations in waste management and policy recommendations for their scaling up. This will mainly concern technical Work packages 1, 2, 3 and 4.

The final phase (M13-M24) will concentrate on the presentation of project results, impact assessment, and the dissemination of comprehensive policy brief on waste management in humanitarian sector. A specific focus will be made on the target local awareness campaign in Kenya and Vietnam to disseminate and support the implementation of improved waste management. This phase also includes the drafting the batch #2 of practice abstracts (8.1) and the final report on dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities (8.2). During the final phase, we will also focus on the dissemination of WP5 “Recycling and WM at field hospitals” and WP6 results “Mitigation and livelihoods”, which are the two technical work packages running until the end of the project. We will share our policy recommendations and results, including the outputs of the Implementation of alternatives through the development of standard operational procedures (SOPs), the examination of waste management from a socio-economic perspective and the assessment of the limits and consequences of introducing bio-based solutions in the humanitarian context.

Overall, this phased approach ensures that communication and dissemination activities are strategically integrated into the project timeline, maximising their effectiveness and impact throughout the entire duration of the WORM project.

4. COMMUNICATION

4.1. WEBSITE

The **project website** (<https://wormproject.eu>) is of crucial importance to enhance the visibility of WORM as it will serve as the main communication tool for the wide dissemination of the project activities, materials, deliverables, and outcomes.

Together with WORM’s social media accounts, the website is a key tool for reaching out to a wide audience, communicate about the project and its results. The website provides essential information on the project, such as its objectives, the grants for schools, resources available, etc.

The following tree structure was designed to ensure that information is easily found by our different target groups.

Figure 4: Tree structure of the WORM website.

The website was launched in April 2024 (M4). It is kept regularly updated, with new content regarding the events, deliverables, and other resources. News article will be regularly published with the latest information about the project activities, thanks to inputs from all project partners.

Figure 5: Homepage of the WORM website.

Social media are being used by the consortium to inform and connect with our different target groups, including IHOs, policymakers, and the scientific community as well as to reach out to the general public (citizens, local communities).

At the start of the project, three social media accounts were opened for WORM: a [LinkedIn page](#), a [Twitter account](#), and a [Facebook page](#). These three platforms each having their specificities and their own userbase, allows us to reach a variety of audiences, in line with our target groups.

- **LinkedIn:** This is currently the main platform for European projects and will allow us to connect with professionals in relevant fields as well as the whole EU ecosystem.
- **Twitter:** This platform is widely used by European projects and by researchers, and policymakers. Due to current instability with the platform, Euronovia will monitor the evolution of the situation and propose alternatives if needed.
- **Facebook:** This platform will allow us to reach our target including the general public, especially during the local campaigns in Kenya and Vietnam.

The three accounts are managed by Euronovia. Partners regularly contribute by sharing news with them and posting through their institutional accounts, as well as personal ones. We are thus able to reach further than the project followers and use the extensive networks of all partners.

We are also ensuring wider dissemination on social media by following and tagging relevant organisations, projects, and other initiatives related to our topics, as well as relevant hashtags (e.g., #wastemanagement #circulareconomy #humanitarian)

Figure 6: WORM LinkedIn page.

Figure 7: WORM Twitter page.

Figure 8: WORM Facebook page.

At M5, the WORM accounts have the following number of followers:

1. LinkedIn: 399 followers
2. Twitter: 29 followers
3. Facebook: 27 followers

The impact of the WORM social media channels is regularly monitored through the platforms' statistics tools to evaluate the best performing posts.

Lastly, targeted local awareness-raising campaigns will be organised and shared on social media, see section 5.4 for further information.

4.2. NEWSLETTERS

A total of **4 newsletters** (twice a year) are planned to be sent out to the newsletter subscribers during the duration of the project. The first newsletter will be sent out at M6. Newsletters will be made available on the project website (<https://wormproject.eu/newsletter/>) and will be disseminated on social media, as well as sent by e-mail to relevant networks of project partners to increase the size of the dissemination list.

4.3. E-PRINTED COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

4.3.1. One-page project description

A one-page project description was created for distribution to participants in any project-related activity. This document contains a simple description of the WORM project and its objectives. The design follows the WORM visual identity and is consistent with the other communication materials developed within the communication package. It is available for download on the project website.

Figure 6: WORM one-page project description.

4.3.2. Leaflets

A first project leaflet with general information on the project was created at M3. It will be distributed to partners for use at any external events that the consortium is organising or attending. It is also available for download on the project website.

Figure 7: WORM leaflet.

A **final leaflet** will also be developed by Euronovia towards the end of the project to present the main achievements of WORM. It will be widely distributed through the project contact database, the website, social networks, and during the WORM final conference at the end of the project.

4.3.3. Roll-up

A roll-up was created using the project’s visual identity and the same graphical elements used in other communication tools. The text content of the roll-up was kept to a minimum as its main functions is the easy recognition of the project during events. This roll-up will be used during internal and external events attended by the consortium to promote and present the project.

Figure 8: WORM roll-up

4.4. AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

Different types of audio-visual materials are planned during the project duration and will be published on the WORM [YouTube channel](#) (@WORM_EUproject).

Figure 12: WORM Youtube homepage.

The following audio-visual materials will be produced and published on YouTube:

1. A **project presentation video** to inform about the project activities in an attractive and dynamic way (by Euronovia at M12).
2. The **2 webinars**.
3. Any additional audio-visual content from the partners.

4.5. PRESS RELATIONS

Specific efforts will be dedicated to press relations in order to ensure a good media coverage about the WORM project at national, and European and international levels. A specific page on the WORM website was also created to gather all content addressed to the press (<https://wormproject.eu/media/>).

1. **Press releases** will be published at M12 and M22. It will also include key information about the project. If relevant, the press release will be adapted and translated in other languages than English by the partners to be shared with their own networks.
2. A **final press kit** will be prepared at the end of the project for massive dissemination of the project final outcomes.
3. Additional press releases may be produced depending on the needs of the partners.

5. DISSEMINATION

5.1. DELIVERABLES

All deliverables will be accessible through the project’s website (<https://wormproject.eu/delivrables/>), with the level of dissemination determining the extent of public availability (Public or Sensitive). In cases where a deliverable is categorized as “sensitive”, a condensed yet informative publishable summary will be provided on the WORM website. This approach ensures transparency while respecting confidentiality concerns. The WORM project has an Open access policy and is oriented towards the sharing of the results to various stakeholders, as almost all deliverables are public (23/24 deliverables). Only one deliverable has a sensitive dissemination level, the D5.2 “Standard operational procedures for handover and recover”, that will be delivered at M24, plus the three ethics requirements deliverables.

5.2. ORGANISATION OF EVENTS

As part of the project activities, the WORM partners are organising several types of events for communication and dissemination purposes, including:

Below is a list of events that will be organised over the course of the project identified in the GA:

- **2 webinars** (M6 & M12)
- **4 workshops** (M6, M12, M18, M24)
- **A targeted local awareness campaign** (See 5.4)
- **A Final conference** organised at the end of the project and co-timed with the final consortium meeting (M24), to present to the various stakeholders the major achievements and final results of the project.

See below a list of planned events organised by the WORM partners.

Type	Title	Date	Location	Partner(s)
Workshop	WORM session during HNPW	May 8, 2024	Geneva, Switzerland	Hanken
Webinar	Innovation friendly Procurement webinar	June 25, 2024	Online	Innovation Norway, CRS
Workshop	Co-design workshop about Sustainability criteria	June 25, 2024	Online	Solvoz & KLU CRS
Webinar	Procurement catalogue presentation	date TBD (end Nov/ early Dec)	Online	Solvoz CRS
Digital and physical focus groups	Focus groups with stakeholders to test feasibility of innovative business models in humanitarian settings	September – October 2024	Online and Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam	Innovation Norway CRS
Workshop	Industry engagement workshops - WORM symposium incl. Validating Business Model Innovation and Plug-and-Play Frameworks for WM Providers in Humanitarian Aid Operations	October 8, 2024	Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam	RMIT

Workshop	Joint workshop with Bio4HUMAN	M11	TBD	TBD
Workshop	Dangers of incinerating mixed waste	M18	TBD	PSA
Workshop	Validation workshop with end users for the CLDs	M18-M20 (TBD)	TBD	KLU, RMIT
Final conference	Final conference	M24	TBD	Hanken, Euronovia

5.3. PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS AND CONFERENCES

Over the course of the project, partners are expected to take part in several **practitioner events and academic conferences** in order to promote WORM and disseminate the outcomes of the project. Below is a preliminary list events divided into two categories. This list will be kept regularly updated by all project partners through a shared Excel file.

Table 2: List of events

Name	Date	Location	Partners planning to attend
Practitioner events			
European Humanitarian forum 2024	March 18-19, 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Hanken, Solvoz
HNPW2024	May 6-10, 2024	Geneva, Switzerland	All – co-timed with WORM GA meeting
AidEX Nairobi	June 14-15, 2024	Nairobi, Kenya	PSA
AidEx	October 23-24, 2024	Geneva, Switzerland	Innovation Norway
African Logistics Conference	2025	TBD	TBD
Kenya Chapter of the International	2025	Kenya	PSA

Association for Public Logisticians			
HNPW2025	17-28 March 2025	Geneva, Switzerland	FRC, Innovation Norway
European Humanitarian Forum 2025	2025	TBD	TBD
Academic conferences			
EurOMA Sustainability Forum	March 4-5, 2024	Hamburg, Germany	KLU
POMS	April 25-29, 2024	Minneapolis, USA	KLU, Solvoz, Hanken
NOFOMA	June 12-14, 2024	Stockholm, Sweden	Hanken
POMS International	June 25-27, 2024	Istanbul, Turkey	Hanken
EURO	July 1-4, 2024	Copenhagen, Denmark	KLU
EURO HOpe	October 3-4, 2024	Madrid, Spain	KLU
POMS	May 8-12, 2025	Atlanta, US	KLU
EurOMA	June 13-18, 2025	Milan, Italy	FRC
Popularization events			
Green Economy Forum & Exhibition	October 21-23, 2024	Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam	KLU
Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival	2025	Brussels, Belgium	TBD
EU Green Week	2025	Several cities in EU	TBD

5.4. TARGETED LOCAL AWARENESS CAMPAIGN

All waste must be handled in a safe and hygienic manner, whereas a significant proportion of waste is also toxic and different treatment options may also result in different levels of toxicity. To disseminate this message, a **targeted and dedicated awareness raising campaign that engages local communities will be organised**. Activities are planned in Kenya (Kisumu County, by PSA) and Viet Nam (VNRC), and in relevant contexts of other end-users (ACF, CRS, ICRC, IMC) who also contribute to the development of relevant materials.

Campaign events engage with:

- Local schools and education programmes to raise awareness about the proper handling of (medical) humanitarian waste, e.g. through school competitions (VNRC) and poetry slams (PSA).
- Local health care facilities (i.e. beyond the deployments of temporary field hospitals) to provide guidance on alternative waste treatment options that are safer and more environmentally friendly.
- Larger stakeholder group (through a workshop that is co-timed with a consortium meeting in M18) to educate a larger audience about the dangers of incinerating mixed waste. Local experts will be invited to speak to add weight to the matter and provide attendees with specialised guidelines and alternative approaches to medical waste treatment.

Brochures, pamphlets, and posters are created for the campaign with information about the hazards of incineration, with the input of health and humanitarian organisations (ICRC, IMC) as well as environmental groups.

Campaign implementation in Kenya engages unemployed youth to distribute brochures in Kisumu County, and the campaign will liaise with the Kenyan Ministry of Sports, Culture, Gender, and Youth Affairs to engage unemployed youth artists to create murals or other visual displays, and creative events such as theatre performances or poetry slams that educate the general public about the hazards of incineration and the alternatives solutions.

5.5. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

WORM is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project. As such, the communication and dissemination activities are not specifically designed for the dissemination of research publications. However, partners will submit and publish the preeminent results of WORM as peer-reviewed articles in environmental management and in operations management journals. They will also publish conference papers. Journal selection will be guided by reaching the relevant target audience and the open access policy of journals. All of these journals are recognised for their global outreach in the relevant community, and e.g. JHLSCM has a full open access policy without any charges from authors. For other potential journals, the WORM project will seek gold open access, and make publications available in open access trusted repositories.

These scientific publications will acknowledge the EU funding by including the following disclaimer:

"This work was supported by the WORM (Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation) project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135392. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

They will follow open access rules as described in section 1.3.

Here is the list of relevant journals that the consortium has identified for the dissemination of the results to the scientific and industrial community:

- Disaster Prevention and Management
- Disasters
- International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction
- International Journal of Operations and Production Management
- Journal of Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management
- Journal of Supply Chain Management
- Waste Management
- Resources, Conservation and Recycling
- Journal of Cleaner Production
- Journal of Environmental Management
- World Development
- Environmental Pollution
- Waste Management & Research: The Journal for a Sustainable Circular Economy
- Journal of International Humanitarian Action
- Production and Operations Management

Scientific publications will also be available on the project's website (<https://wormproject.eu/publications/>).

5.6. POLICY BRIEFS

Policy and decisionmakers at local, national, European, and international levels are one of the target groups clearly identified by the consortium to uptake the project's results and demonstrate their benefits.

To do so, WORM will develop **5 policy briefs** about:

- **Sustainability criteria** (D2.1 - M8)

KLU will combine different sustainable procurement frameworks and adapt them for the humanitarian context, in order to assist the development of sustainability criteria (by Solvoz) for the evaluation of product alternatives (including bio-based alternatives) and their circularity for products prioritised in WORM.

- **Procurement** (D 2.2 - M12)

Based on extant procurement practices of WORM end-users, Solvoz will develop humanitarian procurement guidelines to assist the potential of bio-based solutions to be sought and evaluated in comparative bid analyses.

- **Scaling up** (D3.2 - M12)

Innovasjon Norge will develop policy recommendations that support the uptake and diffusion of effective business models in humanitarian contexts & that support humanitarian organisations in sourcing/procuring innovative solutions/services/models from the private sector.

- **Plug and play framework** (D4.2 - M12)

RMIT will develop a plug and play framework for the easy identification of, and integration with local waste management partners.

- **Medical waste management** (D5.3 - M18)

Considering the need of field hospitals to be able to manage their own waste if local partners are absent or do not have the adequate capacity or waste treatment methods, Solvoz will develop waste management guidelines and policy recommendations for field hospitals that consider alternative waste treatment options, and the implementation and use of bio-based solutions.

These policy briefs will be available on the project website (<https://wormproject.eu/policy-brief/>) and will be widely disseminated in the partners' networks.

5.7. PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

To help innovative and practice-oriented projects share their knowledge in a concise, harmonised, and practice-oriented way, **WORM will share its intermediate and final results through practice abstracts in the EIP-AGRI common format.**

In line with the multi-actor approach, WORM further benefits from the internationality of its consortium including countries with frequent deployments of humanitarian programmes.

Thus, good practices will be identified by the partners based on their own experience, the data collection realised in the Task 1.1, the practices of WORM end users (especially the WORM associated partners) and exchanges with sister and similar projects.

The resulting innovative knowledge will feed into the [European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability](#) (EIP-AGRI) website for broad dissemination to practitioners. End-user material will be produced in the form of several summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format. The EIP common format consists of a set of basic elements characterising the project and includes one or more "practice abstract(s)". The summary of the practice should contain the main results of the activity and the main practical recommendations to the end-users. It should be as interesting as possible for end-users, using a direct and easily understandable language and pointing out elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners.

This format was developed with two main objectives:

- to enable contacting partners and incentivise efficient knowledge exchange.
- to disseminate the results of the project in a concise and easy understandable way to practitioners.

Two batches of practice abstracts are planned during the project:

- **D7.2** - the first batch of practice abstracts should contain 3 practice abstracts (M10).
- **D8.1** - the second batch of practice abstracts should contain 8 practice abstracts (M20).

5.8. CLUSTERING AND SYNERGIES

As a coordination and support action, the WORM project recognises the key role of clustering activities. The project aims not only to maximise its impact by promoting its activities and results, but also to improve the efficiency of its actions and activities by learning from the experiences of other organisations. Therefore, the WORM consortium places particular emphasis on knowledge sharing and networking, seeking to collaborate with individual organisations and experts, as well as with analogous projects with similar funding structures. This collaborative approach is in line with the project's strategy of using collective expertise and experience to optimise its outcomes.

The WORM project underlines the importance of interdisciplinary cross-collaboration with other high impact EU-funded projects, initiatives, and networks as a catalyst for effective communication, dissemination, and outreach efforts. The main objectives of this cross-project collaboration are to explore synergies with our sister project funded under the same call, to establish two-way communication and dissemination channels, to promote the development of innovative ideas, and to promote the formation

of future consortia aligned with the key ideas of WORM, while providing support in resource identification.

In terms of **clustering methodology**, in order to increase the visibility and impact of WORM outcomes and events, the project will identify relevant EU and international projects and initiatives within the first six months. This identification process is a crucial first step in the development of an effective and targeted networking strategy that will be implemented throughout the duration of the project. The research to pinpoint pertinent projects for clustering will primarily commence by exploring initiatives proposed by other consortium partners. This approach leverages the extensive expertise of WORM partners, capitalising on their established networks and collaborations. For each project, the evaluation will consider the overall description of project objectives and activities, along with any additional information available online, to determine their suitability as potential targets for networking activities. This assessment process will be reiterated at the commencement of year 2 of the project. Following the mapping exercise detailed above, the identified projects will be compiled and recorded in an online database accessible through the WORM internal management platform. Regarding the engagement strategy, to establish connections with the identified projects, the coordinators of each project will be reached out to. The initial email will include a brief introduction, along with a presentation outlining the project and suggesting initial collaboration opportunities such as profiling the projects on WORM's website, supporting dissemination and communication through social media accounts, and featuring the projects in the newsletter. At M5, a first list of around 30 similar projects and initiatives has been created and is available on the project Sharepoint. This list has also been shared in the sister project Bio4HUMAN.

Table 3: List of partners involved in humanitarian networks

WORM partners	Networks
Hanken	Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Research Institute (HUMLOG Institute)
Kuhne Logistics University	HELP Logistics
Innovasjon Norge	Humanitarian Innovation Programme
Hanken, KLU and ICRC	Environmental Sustainability in Humanitarian Logistics project (WREC)
Action contre la Faim	Humanitarian Environment Network (REH), Humanitarian Logistics (HULO)
Pamela Steele Associates	International Association of Public Health Logisticians (IAPHL), People that Deliver, the Humanitarian Logistics Association

5.9. CLUSTERING WITH THE SISTER PROJECT

At M5, cooperation has already started with the sister project "Bio4HUMAN - Identifying bio-based solutions for waste management applicable to humanitarian sector" (GA #101135144), funded under the same call, which participated in the WORM kick-off meeting. The activities already launched with Bio4HUMAN are the following:

- Joint kick-off meeting on January 25, 2024;
- Launch and planning of bilateral meetings every 2 months with the two projects coordinators and Communication & Dissemination contact points;
- Promotion of the other project on social media;
- Shared list of similar projects and initiatives we can cluster with;

- Technical meetings and sharing of information (e.g. DG ECHO WORM/Bio4HUMAN meeting on Localisation and protection session on April 16, 2024);
- Inclusion of the sister project in WORM’s GA and workshop at HNPW2024;
- Appearance of the sister project in the WORM website.

The first draft of planned activities until the end of the project are:

- Continuous promotion of the sister project activities on social media and website;
- Joint policy brief (Year 2);
- Shared list of conferences in which each project is participating, create synergies during events;
- Appearance of the sister project in the project video;
- Joint newsletter;
- Participation in the events organised by the project, including Bio4HUMAN invitation to our final conference.

This list will be continuously updated during the project.

The synergies and clustering are enhanced by the participation of several key stakeholders as Associated partners, as well as the participation of the WREC project from the Logistics Cluster as External Advisory Board member.

5.10. FINAL CONFERENCE

A **Final conference** will be organised by Hanken with the support of Euronovia at the end of the project and co-timed with the final consortium meeting, to present to the various stakeholders the major achievements and final results of the project. Sister projects from the call will be invited to the WORM final conference for joint dissemination purposes.

6. EXPLOITATION

WORM consortium will carry out activities to **increase the impact of the results** and to tackle societal problems, in policymaking or for commercial purposes. The objective is to effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn our actions into concrete value and impact for society. The WORM exploitation will be held towards the end of the project and beyond, as soon as exploitable results are available and up to four years after the end of the project.

WORM exploitation strategy will consist of: 1) Creating an attractive knowledge portfolio of key exploitable results (KER); 2) Establishing a community of relevant stakeholders to drive adoption of the KERs; 3) Ensuring a sustainability strategy for all KERs, 4) Detailing partners’ individual strategies for exploitation and/or commercial opportunities tied to innovative services, which could also support the uptake and replication.

The WORM consortium has identified one main exploitable result, indicated in the table below. More may be identified during the second phase of the project.

Table 4: Preliminary list of results with potential of exploitation

Type of result to be exploited	WORM responsible	Target groups	Exploitation and Dissemination to ensure exploitation
Online open-access catalogue for bio-	Solvoz	Academia, NGO, suppliers, companies	Available in open access via the WORM

<p>based solutions for humanitarian actors (and health care actors) including sustainability and technical criteria. A collaborative portal for both private, public and academia to contribute to open-access knowledge sharing of products, solutions, specifications and services. (Upon need, there is a seamless integration for e-sourcing support for NGOs and others).</p>			<p>website. The platform will enable data export in a variety of formats.</p>
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The preliminary list of expected exploitable results identified above will be updated under the lead of Euronovia during RP1 and RP2. All Work Package (WP) leaders will be requested to identify the main exploitable results in their WP and to provide information on each result.

In addition, we will consider making use of the EC tools:

- **Horizon Results Booster** to receive expert guidance and training to improve the project strategy towards effective KER identification and exploitation.
- **Horizon Result Platform** to publish the results.

7. TRACKING THE ACTIONS AND MONITORING THE IMPACT

7.1. TRACKING AND MONITORING OF THE ACTIONS

The partner leading WP5, Euronovia, is responsible for tracking all the communication and dissemination activities of the partners, and use the information to evaluate their impact. At this scope, a document composed of 2 different tabs was created at the beginning of the project to gather data related to the activities implemented by each partner, namely:

- **Communication actions:** partners list and give details about all the communication activities done at the level of their organisation to promote the project.
- **Dissemination activities:** partners list and give details about their dissemination activities aiming to share the project's results.

This document was uploaded to the project management platform and all partners are regularly reminded to update it as soon as they are involved in a communication or dissemination action to keep track of all the activities implemented within WORM.

Communication activity (please select from the drop-down list)	Description of the activity (Max. 200 characters)	Leading partner	Other partners involved	Date (if relevant)	Place	Communication level	Target Audiences (the main target in red)												Communication level	Type of outcome #1	Result of outcome #1	Type of outcome #2	Result of outcome #2	Status		
							Industry/business partners	Innovators	EU institutions	National authorities	Regional authorities	Local authorities	Civil society	Culture	Research communities	Start-ups and other entrepreneurs	Communities (Facebook, LinkedIn, etc.)	Investors							Other (please specify in comments)	
1 Social media	Launch of LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook account	Euronovia	All	21/01/2024	Online	International	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	International	Number of followers	294 (LinkedIn), 24 (X), 21 (Facebook)	Number of posts per year		Delivered
2 EPrinted communication materials	One-page project description	Euronovia	Hanken	03/04/2024	Online	International	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	International					Delivered
3 Print materials	Leaflet	Euronovia	Hanken	15/03/2024	Online	International	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	International					Delivered
4 Print materials	Roll-up	Euronovia	Hanken	15/03/2024	Online	International	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	International					Delivered

Figure 9: Overview of the tracking table

7.2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION IMPACT ASSESSMENT

A detailed communication and dissemination plan was created at M5 in order to check that all activities are planned and are effectively taking place, integrating Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the impact of each dissemination and communication activity. KPIs are a measuring factor for the performance and progress of an activity, message, task, etc. towards its expected impact. Several KPIs were defined for each communication and dissemination activity of the project. They are being used to assess the performance of our activities all along the project duration and potentially re-orientate the dissemination plan if KPIs are not matched, and the expected impact not reached.

Activity	KPIs	End of project objective	Mid-term objective
Webinars	No of webinars / No of attendees per event	2 / 30	1 / 30
Workshops	No of workshops / No of attendees per event	4 / 20	2 / 20
Targeted local awareness campaign	No of campaign	1	N/A
Final conference	No of participants	100	N/A
Joint actions with other EU/international projects	No of actions	4	2
Participation in practitioner events	No of events	2	1
Participation in academic conference	No of conferences	2	1
Website	No of visitors / No of news per year	4,000 / 6	2,000 / 6

Social media	No of followers / No of posts per year	300 / 12	200 / 12
Newsletters	No of issues / No of subscribers	4 / 500	2 / 300
Press releases	No of press releases	2	1
Practice abstracts	No of practice identified	11	4
Project presentation video	No of video	1	N/A
Scientific publications in journal	No of publications	>2	N/A
Policy brief	No of policy brief	5	4
Press media, non-scientific articles	No of articles	4	1

Euronovia will perform an evaluation of these KPIs at mid-term and at the end of the project. The results will be used for the update of the PCDE (D7.3 due at M12) and for the final impact assessment analysis that will be included in the Report on Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach activities (D8.2) which will be submitted at the end of the project (M24). Each KPI will receive a grade Excellent, Good, Moderate, Weak which will allow us to check if we are on track with the work plan. Depending on the results, corrective measures may be considered and implemented.

ANNEX 1 - Schedule of WORM actions

	Year 1												Year 2											
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Logo & visual identity																								
PDEC																								
Communication Package																								
Website																								
Newsletter #1																								
Practice Abstract #1																								
Newsletter #2																								
Press Release #1																								
Motion design video																								
Newsletter #3																								
Practice Abstract #2																								
Press Release #2																								
Newsletter #4																								
Final brochure																								
Final media press kit																								
Final Conference																								

	Year 1												Year 2											
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Communication																								
Dissemination																								
Exploitation																								

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